

Integrative physiological and proteomic signatures provide new insights for deciphering the mechanisms towards drought, salinity, and alkalinity stress tolerances in lentil (*Lens culinaris* Medikus)

PROTEIN-PROTEIN INTERACTION DONE
FOR VARIOUS COMBINATIONS VIA
STRING: FUNCTIONAL PROTEIN
ASSOCIATION NETWORKS

Fig. 4. Protein-protein interaction identified in tolerant genotype in comparison to sensitive under drought condition.

Fig. 5. Protein-protein interaction identified in the tolerant genotype under drought condition in comparison to its control.

Fig. 6. Protein-protein interaction identified in the sensitive genotype under drought condition in comparison to its control.

Fig. 7. Protein-protein interaction identified in tolerant genotype in comparison to sensitive under saline condition.

Fig. 8. Protein-protein interaction identified in the tolerant genotype under saline condition in comparison to its control.

Fig. 9. Protein-protein interaction identified in the sensitive genotype under saline condition in comparison to its control.

